

THE CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH AMIDES. PART XI
THE CONDENSATION OF *m*-TOLYLALDEHYDE

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m-Tolylaldehyde has been condensed with various amides in the presence or absence of an organic base. yielding in each case the corresponding *m*-tolylidene-bisamides.

Following the condensations of *p*-tolylaldehyde with amides (Part III, Mehra and Pandya, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, **9A**, 508), the present paper describes the condensation of *m*-tolylaldehyde with the usual amides in the presence or absence of an organic base like pyridine. The products in all the cases have been shown to be the corresponding *m*-tolylidene-bisamides. The yields are not very high, being below 50%, though on the whole *m*-tolylaldehyde gives slightly higher yields than *p*-tolylaldehyde. Longer heating does not improve the yields and the presence of pyridine accelerates the condensation and slightly increases, in some cases, the yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation with Formamide.—Heating the aldehyde and the amide with a trace of pyridine (1: 2: 0.15 mol.) on a water-bath for 5 hours did not bring about the condensation. Heating at 115° for 8 hours in an open flask resulted in the formation of about 15% of the product. Heating in an oil-bath at 140° for 8 hours increased the yield to 29%, while the maximum of about 48% yield was obtained on heating at 160-170° for 8 hours. Heated also without pyridine, but in the same way in other respects the yield was almost the same, 47.6%. It was also found that heating in a flask provided with a reflux condenser gave no solid, and the aldehyde was recovered unchanged.

The reaction product was first extracted with water to remove the unchanged amide and then crushed with ether in a mortar to remove the remaining aldehyde and then filtered and recrystallised.

The crude product melted at 132-36°. Crystallisation from hot alcohol raised the melting-point ultimately to 139-40°. (Found :N, 14.72. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 14.59 per cent). The bisformamide came out in fine silky needles. It is insoluble in water, ether and benzene; very sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol; more soluble in hot ethyl alcohol or hot acetone. It does not decolourise Baeyer's reagent in alcoholic solution or bromine water. On refluxing with dilute sulphuric acid it breaks down into the aldehyde and the amide. It gives no colour with concentrated sulphuric acid.

With Acetamide.—The aldehyde was heated with acetamide in the same way as above but the temperature of the oil-bath was kept at 115-125° and the heating was continued for 5 hours. The crude product melted at 216° while the pure product melted at 224°. The yields in the absence of pyridine were 40.9% (crude) and 38.6% (pure), in the presence of a trace of pyridine, 50% (crude) and 43.2% respectively. (Found: N 12.92, 13.04. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.73 per cent). Its properties are similar to those of the bisformamide. It is insoluble in water, ether, benzene, acetone and chloroform, sparingly soluble in ethyl acetate and more in hot alcohol.

With Propionamide.—Heating for 5 hours at 115-125° gave 36.3% yield in the presence of a trace of pyridine, and 35.9% in the absence of pyridine. After 2 hours' heating evolution of water vapour and a gradual solidification of the reacting mass were observed, as before.

After the heating, the product was taken out next morning in the usual way. The crude product was fairly pure, as it melted at $194-97^{\circ}$, while the recrystallised (from hot acetone) product melted finally at $200-201^{\circ}$. It came out in white silky flakes, being insoluble in water, ether and ethyl acetate, slightly soluble in cold and more soluble in hot alcohol or acetone. (Found: N, 10'98. $C_{14}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11'29 per cent). Its properties are similar to those of the other products described above.

With n-Butyramide.—Heated in the same way as above, the mixture went into solution in 1 hour and the usual observations were made. The yield, with pyridine, was 39'8%, and in its absence was rather less, 34'4%. The crude bisamide melted at $160-67^{\circ}$, and after two recrystallisations from hot alcohol the final m.p. was $170-71^{\circ}$, 10 hours' heating made no increase in the final yield. (Found: N, 10'36. $C_{16}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10'04 per cent).

With n-Heptamide.—The condensation was much slower and the heating was for 10 hours between $115-25^{\circ}$, 18 hours' heating in another experiment did not increase the yield, which was 35% in the presence of pyridine, and 38'2% in its absence. The crude bisamide melts at $112-16^{\circ}$; recrystallised from hot acetone twice, the m.p. rises to 118° . It is obtained as silky needles, insoluble in water and ether; sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol, soluble in hot acetone or hot ethyl alcohol, very soluble in ethyl acetate. (Found: N, 7'57, 7'63. $C_{22}H_{36}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7'77 per cent).

With Benzamide.—The heating was for 5 hours, but two experiments were made in the presence of pyridine; in the first only 0'15 mol. of pyridine was taken, and in the second, as a white sublimate was seen on the upper portions of the flask, it was continually washed down into the flask with a few more drops of pyridine, in this way a whole molecule of pyridine was used. The yield, however, was identical in both the cases, namely 37'7%, while in the absence of pyridine it was distinctly less, 31'9%. The crude bisamide melted at 186° or slightly above; recrystallised from hot acetone, the m.p. rises finally to 221° . (Found: N, 8'53. $C_{22}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8'13 per cent). Its solubility and other properties are similar to those described above.

With Phenylacetamide.—Phenylacetamide was prepared as before (Pandya and Sodhi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 7A, 367) and was heated with the aldehyde as above, with and without pyridine, for 5 hours between 120° and 130° . The crude yield was very good, m.p. at 184° . On recrystallising from hot alcohol once and from hot acetone afterwards, the final melting point was 199° . The yields were 48'38% in the presence of pyridine and 47% in its absence. (Found: N, 7'17. $C_{24}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7'53 per cent).